

EVALUATION OF UTILIZATION OF ANTENATAL SERVICES BY MOTHERS OF BABIES WITH SEVERE BIRTH ASPHYXIA IN PORT HARCOURT, NIGER DELTA AREA OF NIGERIA.

¹H.A.A.Ugboma and ²C.N.Onyearugha

¹Departments of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. ²Paediatrics, Abia State University Teaching Hospital, Aba , Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

Background

Birth asphyxia has remained a major cause of avoidable neonatal morbidity and mortality in developing countries including Nigeria. Poor or outright non utilization of appropriate health care services in pregnancy and delivery has been implicated as its major risk factor.

Aim: To evaluate the utilization of antenatal services by mothers of babies delivered with severe birth asphyxia at the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH) Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

Method: A case control study of the utilization of antenatal services by 97 mothers of newborns with severe birth asphyxia delivered at UPTH from 1st February to 31st October 2003 compared with mothers of newborns with normal Apgar scores was done. Relevant pregnancy, birth, family and social history were obtained by personal interviews and referral to case notes.

Results: Significantly more of the mothers of babies with normal Apgar score booked early(4 months or less) and had up to 8 or more antenatal visits prior to delivery than mothers of asphyxiated babies 86(88.6%) vs 68(70.2%) p = 0.002; 93(95.7%) vs 68(70.2%) p = 0.001 respectively
Significantly more subjects 56 (57.7%) than the controls 45(46.4%) were primiparous p = 0.04. Also, significantly more subjects 19 (19.5%) suffered delay prior to intervention in labour than the controls 5 (5.1%) p=0.004

Conclusion: Primiparity, delayed booking, inadequate antenatal visits and late intervention in labour have been identified as significant contributors to severe birth asphyxia.

KEYWORDS. Birth asphyxia. Inadequate antenatal visits. Delayed intervention.

INTRODUCTION :

In order to achieve the Millennium Development Goal 4 (to reduce by two-thirds the mortality rate in children aged under five by the year, 2015) neonatal mortality rate needs to be reduced by half (Sule and Onayade ,2006; United Nations, 2001).

Birth asphyxia has remained the major cause of avoidable neonatal morbidity and mortality in developing countries (Ade-Ojo *et al*,2008;Udo *et al*,2008; Onyiriuka and Okolo,2004; Hyder *et al*, 2003; Nem Yen,1992;Udoma *et al*,2001) Though its prevalence in developed countries has decreased drastically, it still remains a major cause of avoidable permanent neurological disability in mature newborns worldwide(Daga and Daga, 2001)

Birth asphyxia often results from poor maternal health, improper management of complications during pregnancy and labour and inadequate resuscitation of the newborn at birth (Fanaroff, 2004; Ellis, 2000; Badawn *et al*, 1998; Manandhar, 2000) . Lack of inadequate utilization of appropriate antenatal and delivery services has often been implicated as a common origin of these problems. Poor or outright non-utilisation of appropriate health care services by expectant women during pregnancy and delivery has been severally reported from different parts of Nigeria and developing countries in general(Ezechukwu *et al*, 2004; Oluwatosin and Adekanmbi, 2004; Obi and Onyire, 2004; Welbeck *et al*, 2003). The high cost of antenatal services and delivery in government and private health establishments unfortunately drives expectant women of the middle and low socioeconomic classes to traditional birth attendants and churches for these services (Lamina *et al*, 2004; Ayaya *et al*, 2004; Etuk and Etuk , 2001; Etuk *et al*,2001).

This study was therefore undertaken to evaluate the utilization of antenatal services by mothers of severely asphyxiated newborns delivered at the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital, Port Harcourt as none has been done previously here to the best of the authors' knowledge. The results obtained shall form a baseline data for future analyses and serve as a veritable tool for formulation of policies aimed at curbing the prevalence of birth asphyxia.

SUBJECTS AND METHOD:

This was a prospective case control study conducted in the main theatre, labour and isolation wards of the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital from 1st February to 31st October 2003. The hospital is a tertiary health institution located in Port Harcourt, the capital of Rivers State. It was founded in 1979 and became baby friendly in the year 1993. Though a tertiary health institution, it also serves as a secondary health care centre since there is only one other secondary health care centre in the densely populated city of Port Harcourt. It is usually well attended because additionally, it serves as a referral centre from peripheral hospitals beyond Rivers State. It has an annual delivery rate of approximately 3000.

Ninety eight mothers whose newborns were delivered at the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital and had severe birth asphyxia were serially recruited as study subjects after obtaining informed consent. One of them died postnatally before being interviewed, so 97 were used for further analysis. Birth asphyxia was defined as Apgar score 1-3 in the first minute of life or equal to or less than five at five minutes. Newborns delivered before arrival at UPTH and those with major congenital malformations were excluded. Also 97 mothers whose newborns had normal Apgar score (8-10 in first minute of life) and within identical weight brackets were consecutively enrolled as controls.

Relevant pregnancy, birth, family and social history was obtained by personal interview using structured questionnaire and referral to case notes. The total number of live births delivered over the study period was derived from obstetric records in the labour and isolation wards and the theatre.

Data was arranged in frequency tables and results were analysed using statistical software EPI- info version 6.04 and SPSS version 11. Student test was used to compare means of variables. P values < 0.05 were considered as significant.

Approval was obtained from the ethics committee of the hospital before commencement of the study.

RESULTS

The total number of live births delivered over the study period was 2064 with 98 being severely asphyxiated giving a prevalence rate of 47 per thousand live births.

However, one of the mothers died postnatally before being interviewed so 97 were used for further analysis.

Among the newborns with severe birth asphyxia there were 53 males and 44 females with male: female ratio of 1.2:1 and those with normal Apgar scores were 56 males 41 females with male: female ratio of 1.3 :1 with the difference between them not being statistically significant $p= 0.76$.

All the controls were booked in UPTH whereas 70.1% of subjects had their booking there. (Table 1)

The median of gestational age (GA) at booking of the subjects was 5 months (range 2 to 9 months) while that of controls was 4 months (range 2 to 7 months). The difference in GA at booking between them is statistically significant.

$P= 0.02$ (Table 1)

The mean of antenatal visits made by the subjects prior to delivery was 6.6 (range 2 to 11) while that of controls was 9 (range 3 to 12 months) with the difference between them being statistically significant. $P= 0.001$ (Table 1).

The range of parity of the subjects was 0 to 7 with a median of 0 while that of controls was 0 to 6 with a median of 1. The difference in parity between the two categories is statistically significant $p= 0.04$. (Table 1).

Though more controls had tertiary education (30.9%) than the subjects (25.7%) there is no significant difference in educational attainment between the two groups $p= 0.64$ (Table 2).

Overwhelming majority of both subjects and controls (94.7% and 99% respectively) were married. (Table 2). The mean age of the mothers of asphyxiated newborns was 28.85 years (range 20 to 38 years) whereas that of controls was 30.94 years (range 23 to 42 years) with the difference between them being significant $p= 0.001$. Significantly more subjects (19.5%) than controls (5.1%) suffered delay prior to intervention in labour $p= 0.004$. (Table 3).

Table 1: Antenatal data of subjects and control

	Number of subjects	%	Number of controls	%	p
Place of booking					
UPTH	68	70.1	97	100	
Private maternity	8	8.2	0	0	
Private clinic	7	7.2	0	0	
PHC	5	5.2	0	0	
Church	5	5.2	0	0	
TBA	4	4.1	0	0	$p = 0.07$
Gestational age at booking (months)					
1-3	12	12.4	14	14.4	
4-6	56	57.7	79	81.5	
7-9	20	20.6	4	4.1	
Unbooked	9	9.3	0	0.0	$p = 0.002$
Number of antenatal visits					
1-3	8	8.2	5	5.2	
4-6	21	21.6	6	6.2	
7-9	53	54.7	54	55.7	
≥ 10	15	15.5	32	32.9	$p = 0.001$
Parity					
0	56	57.7	45	46.4	
1-4	38	39.2	48	49.5	
>4	3	3.1	4	4.1	$P=0.04$
<hr/>					
UPTH	-	University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital			
PHC	-	Primary Health Care			
TBA	-	Traditional birth attendant			

TABLE 2: Sociodemographic data of mothers of newborns with severe birth asphyxia and control.

Educational value level	Number of subjects		Number of control		P
	Number of subjects	%	Number of control	%	
Primary	7	7.2	1	1.0	P=0.64
Secondary	65	67.1	66	68.1	
Tertiary	25	25.7	30	30.9	
Marital Status					
Married	92	94.9	96	99	P=0.09
Unmarried	5	5.1	1	1.0	

TABLE 3

Causes of delay prior to intervention in labour in the subjects and controls

Causes of delay	Number of subjects	%	Number of controls	%	p = 0.004
In labour before intervention					
Delay prior to intervention	19	19.5	5	5.1	
Mothers late recognition of labour	5	5.1	4	4.1	
Labour initially managed in maternity	5	5.1	1	1.0	
Delay in transportation	4	4.1	0	0	
Delay in consent for operation	2	2.1	0	0	
Labour initially managed by TBA	2	2.1	0	0	
Financial constraint	1	1.0	0	0	
TBA Traditional Birth Attendant.					

DISCUSSION

The University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital is the only tertiary health care facility in Rivers State, Nigeria. It is located in the metropolitan capital city of Port Harcourt with a secondary health care facility. Being a Teaching Hospital it has by far greater number of specialist and resident doctors and attracts more referrals from peripheral hospitals in Rivers State and beyond. Its clientele cuts across all strata of the society and quite often come from Niger Delta riverine communities with very difficult terrains. This often results in delayed referrals. Also, patronage of unskilled health practitioners especially traditional birth attendants by pregnant women for massage and delivery is quite rife. The traditional birth attendants are in most cases untrained and hence often unable to recognize complications of pregnancy and labour early and have poor delivery and resuscitation techniques.

The prevalence rate of severe birth asphyxia of 47 cases/1000 live births in this study is quite high. This is lower than 63 cases /1000 live births reported by Omene and Diejemaoh in Benin but higher than 26.5 cases /1000 live births and 36 cases/1000 live births reported by Airede and Olowu from Jos and Ife respectively(Omene and Diejemaoh, 1978; Airede, 1998; Olowu and Olomu,2006).

Perhaps delayed intervention in labour due in part to delay in transit as a result of difficult riverine terrains also contributed to high prevalence of birth asphyxia reported in Benin since both Port Harcourt and Benin city belong to Niger Delta sub region of Nigeria with very difficult riverine topography.

Significantly, more controls (95%) than subjects (70%) booked in either the first or second trimester of pregnancy. Late booking or outright non utilization of antenatal services by pregnant women has been reported previously by several authors as significant risk factors for birth asphyxia (Oluwatosin and Adekanmbi, 2004; Obi and Onyire, 2004; Welbeck *et al*, 2003). Some of these patients come to book only when pregnancy is complicated and they perceive that all is not well. Surprisingly, some well educated occasionally fall into this category. Late booking often makes early detection and prompt management of pregnancy disorders such as pregnancy induced hypertension, toxemia, abnormal lies impossible often resulting in birth asphyxia.

The results of this study also revealed that significantly more controls (33%) had 10 or more antenatal visits prior to delivery than the subjects (15.5%). Paucity of attendance of antenatal care by pregnant women delivering asphyxiated newborns has also been previously reported in Ogun State (Oluwatosin and Adekanmbi, 2004). This practice is quite rife in this community with some pregnant women booking only for the purpose of delivering in the health care facility. In curbing the prevalence of birth asphyxia, the essence of early booking and regular antenatal visits for adequate antenatal supervision and early detection and prompt management of pregnancy complications when they arise cannot be over emphasized.

Significantly, more of the subjects (57.7%) than the control (46.4%) were primiparous. Primiparity has been previously noted as a risk factor for severe birth asphyxia (Ellis, 2000; Badawn *et al*, 1998; Manandhar, 2000). Often the primiparous are ignorant of the demands of pregnancy on themselves and their unborn fetus thereby neglecting early booking and regular attendance for antenatal supervision. These may result in complications leading to birth asphyxia not being detected early and adequately managed.

There was no statistical difference in the educational and marital status of the subjects and control. This could be explained by the fact that large numbers of subjects (92.7%) and control (98.9%) had either secondary or primary education. Similarly, a large population of subjects (94.9%) and control (99.0%) were married.

The mean age of the subjects in this study is significantly less than that of control. Ordinarily, the older the mother the greater the risk of delivery of asphyxiated newborn (Ellis, 2000). This result can be explained by the preponderance of primiparous among the subjects who were generally younger.

The result of this study also revealed that significantly more subjects (19.6%) than the control (5.1%) had delay prior to intervention in labour. Major causes of delay were mothers' late recognition of labour (25%), labour initially managed in a maternity (25%), delay in transportation (20%). The primiparous are often naïve and sometimes unaware that they are in labour even with complications such as abnormal lie, prolonged labour, particularly when they are irregular in antenatal attendance.

Often pregnant women have their antenatal supervision and deliveries in private maternities. These maternities are often manned by untrained and inexperienced staff who fail to detect problems in pregnancy and labour early resulting in late referrals. Delay in transportation may be due to lack of vehicle or difficult terrains and roads leading to delayed arrival at an appropriate health facility. All these may result eventually in birth asphyxia or even still birth.

CONCLUSION:

Mothers of newborns with severe birth asphyxia were predominantly primiparous. They also booked late in pregnancy, had inadequate antenatal visits prior to delivery and delayed intervention in labour.

Health education via the electronic and print media, market women organizations, community leaders, community gatherings, faith based organizations and persons concerned with pre-marital counseling emphasizing the need for early booking and regular antenatal attendance as well as delivery in appropriate health care facility by expectant women must be commenced and sustained.

There must be organization of various seminars and workshops for employees of private health institutions, primary health centers and traditional birth attendants on early recognition of complications of pregnancy and labour and prompt referral of cases to appropriate health care facility.

Health care facilities manned by properly trained staff should be sited within 5 kilometres or 30 minutes walking distance from communities.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We are immensely grateful to the obstetricians, anaesthesiologists and the nursing staff of the main theatre, postnatal and isolation wards and the Special Care Baby Unit for their cooperation in the course of the study.

REFERENCES

Ade-Ojo I.P, Loto O.M. (2008) Outcome of eclampsia at Ile-Ife, Nigeria. Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice, 11(3): 279-284.

Airede A.I. (1998) Birth asphyxia and hypoxic ischaemic encephalopathy: Incidence and severity. Nig Med Pract 30: 58-62.

Ayaya S.O, Esamai F.O, Rotich J, Lietchy E. (2004) Perinatal mortality in the special care nursery of Moi Teaching and Referral Hospital, Eldoret, Kenya. E Afr Med J, 8: 555-561.

Badawi N, Kurinczuk J. J, Keogh J. M, Alessandri . M, O'Sullivan F, Burton P. R, *et al.* (1998). Intrapartum risk factors for newborn encephalopathy: the Western Australian case-control study. BMJ. 5; 317(7172):1554–1558

Daga A.S, Daga S.R. (2001) Antecedent risk factors of neonatal asphyxia in term newborns. Semin Perinatol, 23: 226-33

Ellis M, Manandhar N. Manandhar D.S.(2000) Risk factors for Neonatal N Encephalopathy in Kathmandu, Nepal Br Med J, 320: 1229-36. encephalopathy. Br Med J, 317: 1549-53.

Etuk S.J, Asuquo E.E.J, Itam I.H, Ekanem A.D. (2001) Reasons why booked women deliver outside orthodox health facilities in Calabar, Nigeria. Int J Social Science and Public Policy 2(1): 90-102.

Etuk S.J, Etuk I.S. Relative risk of birth asphyxia in babies of booked women who deliver in unorthodox health facilities in Calabar, Nigeria. Acta Tropica 2001; 79: 143-47.

Ezechukwu C.C, Ugochukwu E.F, Egbuonu I, Chukwuka J.O. (2004) Risk factors for neonatal mortality in a regional tertiary hospital in Nigeria. Nig J Clin Pract, 7: 50 – 52.

Fanaroff A. (2000) Birth Asphyxia. Neonatol, 4:506.

Hyder A.A, Wali S.A, McGuckin J. (2003). The burden of disease from neonatal mortality: a review of South Asia/sub-Saharan Africa. Brit J Obstet Gynae. An International Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, 110: 894-901.

Lamina M.A, Sule-odu A.O, Jagun E.O. (2004) Factors militating against delivery among patients booked in Olabisi Onabanjo University Teaching Hospital Sagamu, Nigeria. Nigerian Journal of Medicine, 13(1): 52-55.

Manandhar M.S, Wyatt P. (2000) Stillbirth and Neonatal encephalopathy in Kathmandu Nepal. An estimate of the contribution of birth asphyxia to perinatal mortality in a low-income urban population. Pediatr Perinat Epidemiol, 14: 39-42.

Nem Yen B. (1992) Factors associated with clinically significant Perinatal Asphyxia in Malaysian Neonates J Trop pediatr, 38: 282-289.

Obi S.N, Onyire B.N. (2004) Pattern of neonatal admission and outcome at a Nigerian Tertiary Health Institution. Orient J Med, 16: 31-37.

Olowu W.A, Olomu S.C. (2006) Birth Asphyxia: Risk factors for Mortality. Nig Med Pract, 31: 69-72.

Oluwatosin M.T, Adekanmbi A. (2004) Findings on the use of antenatal facilities in Ogun State. Nig Med Pract, 45:68-71.

Omene J.A, Diejomaoh P.M.E. (1978) Analysis of 226 asphyxiated infants at the University of Benin Teaching Hospital (1974-1976). Nig J Paediatr 5:25-29.

Onyiriuka N.A, Okolo A.A. (2004) Perinatal outcome in patients with preeclampsia in Benin City, Nigeria. Trop J Obstet Gynaecol,21(2):148-152.

Sule A.A, Onayade J. (2006) Community based antenatal and perinatal interventions and newborn survival. Nigerian Journal of Medicine, 15: 108-118.

Udo J.J, Anah M.U, Ochigbo S.O, Etuk I.S, Ekanem A.D. (2008) Neonatal mortality and morbidity in Calabar, Nigeria: A hospital-based study. Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice, 11(3): 285-289.

Udoma E.J, Udo J.J, Etuk S.J. (2001) Morbidity and Mortality among infants with Normal Birthweight in a Newborn Baby Unit Nig J Paediatr, 28: 13-17.

United Nations General Assembly-56th Session: Road map toward the implementation of the United Nations Millennium Declaration: report of the Secretary-General. (2001) New York: United Nations,

Welbeck J, Biritwum R.B, Mensah G. (2003) Factors affecting the survival of the "at risk" newborn at Korle Bu Teaching Hospital Accra, Ghana. W Afr J Med, 22: 55-8.

Received for Publication: 12/11/2010

Accepted for Publication: 14/12/2010

Corresponding Author:

H.A.A.Ugboma

Departments of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital, Port Harcourt, Nigeria.